

**MEDIATING ROLE OF FREE CHOICE IN THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN
FINANCIAL VARIABLES AND WELL-BEING: DATA FROM WORLD
VALUES SURVEY WAVE 7 OF THE PHILIPPINES**

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Mediating Role of Free Choice in the Relationship Between Financial Variables and Well-Being: Data from World Values Survey Wave 7 of the Philippines

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to explore the mediating effect of Free Choice on the relationship between financial-related variables, such as Financial Situation and Income, and subjective well-being constructs, namely Life Satisfaction and Happiness. Data from the 2019 World Values Survey were utilized. The study selected relevant questions related to the constructs being investigated: Income (Q288), Financial Situation (Q50), Free Choice (Q48), Life Satisfaction (Q49), and Happiness (Q46). Structural Equation Modeling was conducted to determine the indirect effects of Free Choice. The results revealed that across all social classes, Financial Situation predicts Life Satisfaction. Additionally, the Financial Situation also contributes to Happiness, except in the upper class. However, Free Choice mediates the relationship between Financial Situation and Life Satisfaction, but not Happiness, only among the middle class. These findings help to understand how financial situations affect subjective well-being (life satisfaction and happiness) differently across social classes, particularly clarifying the varying mediating role of Free Choice in this relationship. Private and public organizations can utilize this knowledge to develop policies related to financial security and well-being. It is recommended that the model investigated be validated using objective measures and multi-item measurements of constructs.

Keywords: *subjective well-being, philippines, world values survey, psychology*

Introduction

Life satisfaction is one of the three components of subjective well-being (SWB), along with positive affect and negative affect. It is widely accepted as a “cognitive evaluation of one’s life” (Diener et al., 1985). Although related to PA and NA, life satisfaction is distinct (Lucas et al., 1996). There are two competing notions about how people evaluate their lives. According to Schwarz and Strack (1999), people base their evaluations on available information rather than carefully assessing their lives. This evaluation can be influenced by temporal factors such as mood (Schwarz & Clore, 1983; Sinclair & Mark, 1995) and even the sequence of administration of other tests alongside the life satisfaction scale (Strack et al., 1988). On the other hand, some researchers argue that life satisfaction judgment is based on chronically available information, making it relatively stable (Schimmack & Oishi, 2004; McNamee & Mendiola, 2014; Lucas et al., 2018).

Numerous factors play a role in one’s life satisfaction judgment. In the latest systematic review of Khodabakhsh (2022) on the factors affecting life satisfaction in Asia, there are factors of life satisfaction among adults. Some of these are cognitive ability, economic status, education level, social functioning, social support, and the like. Cognitive ability is a strong predictor of life satisfaction among people without cognitive impairments. On the other hand, those with cognitive impairments, their life satisfaction tend to be affected significantly by their social relationships. Economic stability such as medical care, economic activities, and household assets is found to be a factor of life satisfaction. Its effect is more profound with more affluent individuals. Moreover, higher education levels are linked to greater life satisfaction among older adults in East, South, and Southeast Asia.

Certain sociodemographic variables are predictors of life satisfaction. In the study of Fernández-Ballesteros (2001), higher life satisfaction level is linked with the following factors: being young, men, and those who are married, well-educated, and have higher incomes report higher life satisfaction. Income and education mediate the effects of age and gender. In the same study, Psychosocial factors, particularly activity and health, have a significant relationship with life satisfaction in old age. Activity, including physical and social engagement, directly enhances life satisfaction by promoting positive self-view and well-being. Perceived health, reflecting subjective assessments, and physical illness, representing objective health conditions, are also crucial, with perceived health being a stronger predictor of satisfaction. This study utilized World Happiness 2020 data.

On the other hand, the relationship between psychological factors and life satisfaction is not simple. There are factors such as age that could affect the said relationship. In the study of Oladipo (2013), they found out that among the youth sample (undergraduate students), the relationship between motivation and life satisfaction is not how it is usually observed. High need achievement motivation combined with internal locus of control is related to low life satisfaction. On the other hand, youth with low need achievement motivation and at the same time, have external locus of control tend to have higher levels of life satisfaction. This can be explained by the idea that individuals with a high need for achievement are often never fully satisfied and continuously pursue higher goals, which can lead to anxiety and dissatisfaction. In contrast, those who attribute outcomes to external factors and do not actively seek improvement may adopt a more passive and contented approach to life.

Among the old age population, it is physical health that significantly predicts levels of life satisfaction. Physical health is a predictor of life satisfaction among older people because it directly influences psychological well-being, which in turn affects life satisfaction.

The study found that physical condition, as measured by Barthel's index, was positively related to life satisfaction, indicating that better physical health contributes to higher life satisfaction (Meléndez, 2009).

As additional support for the complexity of creating life satisfaction judgments, personality is also known to influence life satisfaction. Extraversion, neuroticism, and conscientiousness directly predict life satisfaction. Specifically, extraversion and conscientiousness positively influence life satisfaction by enhancing social relationships and personal achievement, while neuroticism negatively impacts it due to its association with emotional instability. Additionally, findings suggest that personality traits affect how individuals perceive their self-concept, including aspects like physical attractiveness and relationships, which in turn influence life satisfaction (Parker, 2008).

Life Satisfaction in Asia and Europe

Focusing on social variables, life satisfaction in Asia is influenced by national pride and religiosity. In collectivistic contexts, national pride significantly affects an individual's life satisfaction judgment. Religiosity influences life satisfaction through the joy and positive emotions promoted by the experience-oriented traditions of Asian religions. In contrast, in European countries, life satisfaction is not significantly attributed to nationalism and religiosity. This is expected because European countries place more importance on rationalization and secularization, transforming religious practices into less joy-inducing activities. Additionally, rationalization relates to life satisfaction by promoting autonomy and individualization. However, a similar trend can be observed in economically successful Asian countries like Hong Kong and Japan, which often report lower life satisfaction. This is attributed to weaker social integration due to diminished emphasis on religious and nationalistic values. Thus, the relationship between social variables and life satisfaction is shaped by socio-cultural and economic factors (Jagodzinski, 2010).

More importantly, as the mentioned studies on life satisfaction as attributed to financial variables, there is a study that focuses on a comparison between Asia and Europe in terms of the relationship between various economic variables and life satisfaction (Jagodzinski, 2010). It was found that in Asia, the standard of living has a strong connection with life satisfaction. Particularly, household income contributes to the life satisfaction judgments of people in Asian countries. In Europe, the converse is observed. Income has a relatively weak relationship with life satisfaction. It is the economic development (as measured by GNP per capita) which a strong predictor of life satisfaction in Europe.

The economic status of countries significantly affects the life satisfaction of their citizens. While socio-demographic factors and cultural values impact life satisfaction, their relationship with life satisfaction is influenced by a country's development status. Marriage generally correlates with higher life satisfaction in developed countries, while divorce or separation has a notably negative impact on men in less developed countries, potentially due to entrenched traditional gender roles. The significance of educational attainment varies, being particularly relevant for men in developed nations. Employment status universally improves happiness, except for women in less developed countries, where traditional roles may influence this outcome. In developed economies, family importance significantly enhances life satisfaction. Conversely, in less developed countries, the importance of religion notably boosts life satisfaction for both men and women. Interestingly, income positively impacts life satisfaction regardless of whether the country is developed or less developed (Lange, 2010). The study by Eksi and Kaya (2017) reveals that subjective well-being (life satisfaction) is significantly influenced by global relative deprivation, defined as the gap between a country's income and the average income of wealthier countries. Clark et al. (2010) also found that individuals' subjective well-being is more impacted by their income rank relative to others rather than by the average income of their comparison groups. This perspective aligns with Campbell's (1976) explanation that individuals form life satisfaction judgments by comparing their current life satisfaction with others, as well as with their past and future experiences.

Within the context of Asia, life satisfaction is influenced by income, with a more pronounced effect in low-income countries. Income plays a critical role in enhancing life satisfaction, particularly between the poor and middle-income groups, rather than between middle and high-income groups. This indicates that higher income significantly boosts life satisfaction for the poor but has a lesser impact on the affluent, highlighting the importance of poverty alleviation in these regions. Thus, education in Asia is seen as instrumental in securing better jobs and higher incomes, which in turn improves life satisfaction (Ngoo et al., 2015).

The significant difference between developing and developed countries in the relationship between economic variables, such as income and life satisfaction, can be explained by the processes behind their expenditures. When basic needs are met, expenditures on essential items do not significantly affect life satisfaction. In developed countries, life satisfaction becomes attributed to factors related to status, luxury, and social comparisons. In developing countries, spending on utilities and basic food items has a pronounced impact on life satisfaction, as these expenditures are crucial for meeting fundamental needs and positively influence well-being (Dumludag, 2015).

In Southeast Asian countries, the happiness index is significantly influenced by the gross domestic product (GDP) index. This relationship is especially apparent in less developed countries such as Myanmar, Cambodia, and Laos. These countries, with lower economic conditions, also exhibit less favorable health and social support indicators. In the case of Laos, which has the lowest scores in happiness, health, economy, and family support, this correlation is particularly striking. This illustrates the impact of financial status on life satisfaction: better economic conditions generally lead to higher life satisfaction, as reflected by the positive correlation between economic indicators and happiness scores.

Bad financial status undoubtedly influences one's mental health. Students facing high levels of stress and challenges in university life, including financial difficulties and interpersonal relationship issues, may struggle with their life satisfaction. In less developed countries, financial constraints can limit access to coping strategies and stress management techniques. This lack of resources, in turn, negatively impacts their life satisfaction (Aning & Seok, 2012).

Free Choice as Mediator between Financial Variables and Life Satisfaction

Material wealth is deemed to be important among developing countries as it is instrumental in fulfilling survival needs (Inglehart, 1997; Diener et al., 2013; Dumludag, 2015; Ngamaba et al., 2020). Having a good status in terms of financial situation means that one is not too constrained by financial obligations. Such a person has considerable freedom and perceived control over things in life (Van Kerckhove et al., 2020). When these basic needs are sufficient due to having good financial resources, prioritization of these needs is usually reduced. Thus, people tend to feel they have the ability to consider multiple purchase options (Shah et al., 2015).

Having some degree of autonomy or freedom, individuals tend to have more influence on their desired outcomes or make personal choices which greatly improve their life satisfaction (Ng, 2015). As in the case of autonomy and self-regulation, when individuals experience a sense of autonomy in their actions, they are more likely to engage in self-regulation that aligns with their true values and interests rather than external pressures (Carver & Scheier, 2000). This alignment fosters a more authentic and intrinsic motivation, leading to higher life satisfaction. Related to this, self-determination theory holds that individuals' perception of autonomy is related to greater well-being. This also serves as a protective factor against depressive symptoms (Chirov & Ryan, 2011). This also suggests that retail therapy might work as it encourages the client to have a choice to make purchases that help them to feel in control over their environment which improves their well-being (Rick et al., 2014).

On the other hand, Barry Schwartz (2015) presents an argument that emphasizes that having more choices can lead to less satisfaction with our decisions. Certain individuals become overwhelmed by the choices available to them because they are "maximizers." These people continuously compare the products they bought both before and after the purchase, often leading to feelings of dissatisfaction. On the other hand, "satisfiers" settle for something good enough and are not preoccupied with the possibility that there might be a better option out there. Related to this, in the creation of the Saunders Consumer Orientation Index (SCOI; a scale that assesses the level to which someone perceives themselves as a commodity), it was assumed that the scale is negatively related to life satisfaction (measured by the Satisfaction with Life Scale; Diener et al., 1985). This implies that having a lifestyle focused on the acquisition and possession of material goods would predict lower life satisfaction. A person shifts the basis of personal value (such as free choice or autonomy) to external possessions (Saunders & Munro, 2000). Thus, such a person is controlled by a purchasing mindset.

Thus, variables related with autonomy such as free choice might mediate the relationship between financial variables and life satisfaction. However, the studies present differing views on how independence and freedom impact one's life satisfaction.

Research Questions

The present study investigated the mediating role of free choice in the relationship between financial variables (such as income and financial satisfaction) and subjective well-being (life satisfaction and happiness). This mediation model was validated in the Philippines using World Values Survey 2019 data. Additionally, the moderating effect of subjective social status was examined to determine if the hypothesized model varies among low, working, middle, and upper-class individuals. This study aims to specifically answer the following research questions:

1. Does free choice mediate the relationship between financial situation and subjective well-being (happiness and life satisfaction) among Filipinos of different social classes?

Methodology

Respondents

The study's participants are residents of the Philippines aged 18 and above. Participation in the World Values Survey (WVS) is not restricted to Philippine citizens. The sample size is 1,200, with an equal distribution of females and males. The sample represents 95% of the country's population. A probabilistic sampling method, specifically stratified sampling, was employed. Data collection methods include internet panel surveys, postal surveys, and telephone interviews (WVS, n.d.).

Instrument

In the study, the researcher selected items corresponding to the variables and constructs under investigation. These items include the following questions: Financial Situation (Q50): "How satisfied are you with the financial situation of your household? Please use this card again to help with your answer." Life Satisfaction (Q49): "All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole these days?" Free Choice (Q48): "Please use this scale where 1 means 'no choice at all' and 10 means 'a great deal of choice' to indicate how much freedom of choice and control you feel you have over the way your life turns out." Income (Q288): "On this card is an income scale on which 1 indicates the lowest income group and 10 the highest income group in your country. We would like to know in what group your household is." Happiness (Q46): "Taking all things together, would you say you are Very happy, Rather happy,

Not very happy, or Not at all happy?" Social Class (Q187): "People sometimes describe themselves as belonging to the working class, the middle class, or the upper or lower class." Q46, Q49, and Q50 are reversely keyed items and were changed to positive keying for the analysis. Additionally, for Q187, the categories "Lower middle class" and "Upper middle class" were merged. Respondents with missing data were omitted from the analysis.

It should be noted that all the measures are self-report and single-item (SI). In psychometrics, it is widely accepted that a construct should be represented by multiple indicators to ensure its validity (Kline, 1999). However, there are studies that utilize single-item measures (e.g., Idler & Benyamini, 1997; Wanous et al., 1997; Blake & McKay, 1986; Wanous & Hudy, 2001; Elo et al., 2003; Postmes et al., 2013; Syrophioulus, 2020). The question is, "When is a single-item measure warranted for use?"

According to Ainley and Patrick (2006), when the construct is easily understood by laypeople, a single-item measure could be used. In the case of life satisfaction, there is an ongoing debate about whether it should be assessed through objective or subjective indicators (e.g., Kubiszewski et al., 2018; Mackū et al., 2020), and whether single-item or multiple-item measures should be used (e.g., Cheung & Lucas, 2014; Jovanović & Lazić, 2020). Despite this debate, life satisfaction is generally understood by laypeople as simply how satisfied they are with their lives. While individuals may have various domain references for evaluation, they are still capable of providing an estimation. Additionally, people use their perception to evaluate their life satisfaction, making a single-item measure an appropriate assessment tool (Rossiter, 2002; Rossiter, 2011).

Data Analysis

The researcher chose to use regression-based structural equation modeling (SEM) to analyze the survey data instead of mediation analysis (e.g., Baron & Kenny, 1986). Mediation analysis assumes causality and a temporal ordering of predictor, mediator, and outcome variables. In causal relationships, variables can be classified as causes and effects, which cannot be analyzed by standard regression due to the need for a priori assignment of each variable as either a cause or effect (MacKinnon & Fairchild, 2009).

SEM was used because it allows for a single analysis of variables that serve as mediators, predictors, and outcomes in a hypothesized model. In contrast, standard regression requires an ad hoc method to determine indirect and total effects (Sobel, 1982; Baron & Kenny, 1986; Clogg et al., 1992; MacKinnon, 2008; Bollen & Pearl, 2013).

When creating a hypothesized model with different paths, SEM can estimate if the collected data fits the proposed model by providing model fit information. This serves as empirical support for the assumptions of a mediational model (Imai & Tingley, 2010; Bollen & Pearl, 2013).

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

The overall sample size is $n = 1,200$, with the social classes composed of $n = 259$ individuals in the low class, $n = 170$ in the working class, $n = 737$ in the middle class, and $n = 34$ in the upper class. The variables included in the analysis are financial situation ($M = 6.32$, $SD = 2.58$), free choice ($M = 6.77$, $SD = 2.59$), life satisfaction ($M = 7.37$, $SD = 2.47$), happiness ($M = 3.42$, $SD = 0.68$), and income ($M = 4.39$, $SD = 2.08$). See Table 1 for the descriptive statistics of the whole sample. The sample size, mean, and standard deviation of variables per social class are presented in Table 2.

Model Fit Indices

The model demonstrates acceptable values for indices of absolute, incremental, and parsimonious fit.

For the absolute fit, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is $RMSEA = .00$, meeting the acceptable value suggested by Browne and Cudeck (1992). The Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) is $GFI = 1$, exceeding the .90 threshold proposed by Jöreskog and Sörbom (1984). Additionally, the chi-square of the model is nonsignificant, with $p = .59$, as recommended by Wheaton et al. (1977).

In terms of incremental fit, all indices are at acceptable levels. The Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI) is $AGFI = 1$, surpassing the ideal value of .90 suggested by Tanaka and Huba (1985). The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is also at an acceptable value, with $CFI = 1$, greater than the .90 benchmark set by Bentler (1990). The Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) is $TLI = 1$, meeting the recommended value of greater than .90 by Bentler and Bonett (1980). Finally, the Normed Fit Index (NFI) is $NFI = 1$, aligning with Bollen's (1989) recommendation of greater than .90.

The parsimonious fit of the model, measured by dividing the chi-square by the degrees of freedom, is within the acceptable range of less than 3, with a value of $\text{chisq}/df = .81$, as suggested by Marsh and Hocevar (1985). See Table 3 for the model fit indices of the model.

Regression Analyses

Among all social classes, the financial situation positively predicts life satisfaction: low class ($\beta = .33$, $p < .001$), working class ($\beta = .38$, $p < .001$), middle class ($\beta = .46$, $p < .001$), and upper class ($\beta = .47$, $p < .001$). Additionally, the financial situation positively predicts happiness in the low ($\beta = .27$, $p < .001$), working ($\beta = .17$, $p = .04$), and middle classes ($\beta = .18$, $p < .001$).

The financial situation also positively predicts free choice only in the working ($\beta = .17, p = .05$) and middle classes ($\beta = .13, p = .002$). However, only in the middle class does free choice positively predict life satisfaction ($\beta = .13, p < .001$) and happiness ($\beta = .09, p = .02$). Furthermore, income positively predicts the financial situation in the middle class only ($\beta = .12, p = .003$). See Table 4 for the complete regression analyses of the variables per social class.

Indirect Effects

Among middle-class Filipinos, free choice mediates the relationship between financial situation and life satisfaction ($\beta = .33, p = .02$). However, the financial situation does not show a significant indirect effect on life satisfaction through free choice ($\beta = .01, p = .07$) in the same social class.

Regarding the mediating effect of the financial situation between the relationship of income and life satisfaction and happiness, it is found that only among middle-class individuals does income have an indirect effect on life satisfaction ($\beta = .06, p = .004$) and happiness ($\beta = .02, p = .02$). See Table 5 for all the indirect effect statistics.

Predicted Variability

Among the endogenous variables, life satisfaction exhibits the highest percentage of variability attributed to its predictors. Specifically, 24.30% of the variability in life satisfaction among the middle class is attributed to both financial situation and free choice.

In contrast, for the other three social classes, the variability in life satisfaction is attributed solely to the financial situation. For the low, working, and upper classes, 22.90%, 14.90%, and 30.50% of the changes in life satisfaction, respectively, are attributed to the financial situation.

The predicted variance of happiness attributed to the financial situation and free choice in the middle class is 4.40%. In contrast, in the other social classes, happiness is not predicted by free choice. For the low, working, and upper classes, 7.40%, 6.40%, and 7.30% of the changes in happiness, respectively, are attributed to the financial situation. See Table 6 for the predicted variabilities of dependent variables in the model.

The analysis of World Values Survey (WVS) Wave 7 data for the Philippines found that the financial situation positively predicts life satisfaction across all social classes. This finding supports the idea that in developing countries like the Philippines, life satisfaction is strongly influenced by financial situation, as the ability to purchase necessities depends on financial resources (Ngamaba et al., 2020). This can be explained by the scarcity hypothesis, which suggests that people's priorities are shaped by their socio-economic environment. Therefore, individuals place the highest subjective value on things, such as finances, that are in relatively short supply (Inglehart, 1997). Additionally, the role of free choice in the relationship between financial situation and life satisfaction varies depending on social class.

Subjective Well-being of Middle, Lower, and Working Class

Only among individuals who perceive themselves as middle class does free choice mediate the relationship between financial situation and life satisfaction. Middle-class individuals generally worry less about their financial obligations, allowing them to express their independence and personal preferences. This ability to stand out from their lower-class counterparts and develop their interests contributes to what is known as "expressive independence" (Stephens et al., 2014). They also have psychological and material resources that enhance their sense of free choice, which they use to influence their social outcomes (Kraus et al., 2012).

Kraus et al. (2009) found that lower-class individuals tend to attribute their circumstances externally, accepting income inequality as beyond their control. Growing up with fewer resources, people in the lower class often believe they have little control over their outcomes (Kraus et al., 2012). Despite the insignificance of the regression analysis between free choice and happiness in the lower and working classes, individuals in these social strata still experience a sense of freedom. However, their perception of independence may focus more on the quality rather than the quantity of their choices. This concept, known as "Qualitative Freedom," emphasizes meaningful choices beyond material wealth and considers factors like human dignity, reasonableness, and reciprocity, advocating for a balanced approach to economic, political, and cultural freedoms (Dierksmeier & Dierksmeier, 2019).

In contrast, happiness is directly predicted by financial situations across all social classes, except for the upper class. Free choice does not mediate this relationship. For instance, in Japan, greater household savings and investments, which are indicative of a better financial situation, are associated with higher levels of self-reported happiness (Mimura, 2023). Research consistently shows that higher incomes correlate with greater happiness, although this effect levels off at a certain point (Kahneman & Deaton, 2010).

Overall, while free choice supports an individual's autonomy needs and is closely linked to life satisfaction (Steckermeier, 2021), happiness—considered an emotional component of subjective well-being (Lucas et al., 1996)—is influenced by financial circumstances through factors beyond free choice alone.

Upper Class

When individuals have ample resources, they often feel a sense of independence because they can influence their environment. However, the relationship between financial situation and life satisfaction in the upper class is not necessarily mediated by free choice

for several reasons.

Firstly, perceived social class does not always align with one's actual wealth or financial situation. For instance, a survey revealed that one-quarter of millionaires do not consider themselves affluent (Business News Daily, 2020). Additionally, higher income alone does not lead to happiness unless it is spent. Spending is often viewed as a way to compensate for work efforts, leading individuals to feel pressured to spend their money to feel rewarded (Tov et al., 2018).

Moreover, those in the upper class may feel compelled to match the consumption habits of their peers. This brings satisfaction as it signals high social status, but it also restricts their choices. They may feel obligated to purchase specific products or experiences to maintain their social standing (Chancellor & Lyubomirsky, 2011; Lyubomirsky et al., 2005). While free choice and autonomy generally enhance subjective well-being and life satisfaction, too much freedom can be detrimental, potentially leading to increased stress (Schwartz, 2004).

Conclusions

Financial situation is very important in developing countries such as the Philippines. It is proven that it is associated with subjective well-being (life satisfaction and happiness) because it functions as a means for securing basic needs. Moreover, feelings of free choice are important in understanding how financial situations affect subjective well-being. It functions differently depending on the social class of the Filipinos.

Having low financial resources could be framed by individuals in low and working social classes as related to having little control over things. However, it should be noted that freedom could also be attributed to these individuals as related to post-material aspects like family life, social relationships, personal values, and community involvement.

In the middle class, their financial situation allows them to freely do things such as purchasing out of leisure or spending their resources on things that enhance their life satisfaction. As for the upper class, their financial affluence does not necessarily give them the feeling of being free. Instead, the abundance of financial resources and ability to purchase might lead to being pressured to maintain the high social status they get from expensive material things.

Free choice does not explain the relationship between financial situation and happiness among low, working, and middle class. This is expected as happiness is theoretically different from life satisfaction. The existence of the relationship between financial situation and happiness might be explained by other psychological constructs.

Since the WVS consists of single-item measures for some psychological constructs, it is often assumed that these measures are error-free. This rationale is applied to constructs that are easily understood by individuals, such as satisfaction with life or other life domains, where satisfaction judgments are generally subjective (Hair et al., 2009). Moreover, researchers often use single-item measures because they are practical; they allow for the collection of a large amount of data quickly from survey respondents, who may come from diverse populations (e.g., WVS) (Fuchs & Diamantopoulos, 2009). However, it is advisable to use multi-item measures when the constructs being measured are more complex than their single-item counterparts. Multi-item measures allow for the establishment of reliability checks beyond just test-retest reliability.

It is recommended to test the overall hypothesized model of the present study, or its specific paths, using multi-item measures. Results from studies that used single-item measures still hold merit and should be considered as exploratory inquiries into possible associations between variables related to health and national conditions among different countries, as in the case of the WVS. Therefore, it is advisable to further investigate the findings derived from such measures.

There is ongoing debate regarding the use of objective versus subjective measures of life satisfaction (e.g., Nakamura et al., 2018; Macku et al., 2020; Nakamura & Managi, 2020). The measures included in the present study are subjective. Therefore, future research could validate the results of this study using objective measures.

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